

north american
academic research

Research

Palm Leaf Manuscripts (Pe Sar)

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Accepted: 25 August, 2019 ; *Online:* 30 August, 2019

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3382013>

Abstract : *Behind the existing of literature, we want to know about the letters which were written on something. In particular, palm leaves were mostly used. Palm leaves were easily available in large number, and writing on palm leaves was easier than other. So they were dutiful for writing. In this paper, therefore, palm leaf manuscripts and their background history will be presented according to periods and regions.*

Keywords : *Pe Sar, Palm leaf Manuscripts, palm leaf inscriptions.*

Introduction

It is palm leaf manuscripts that have propagandized the Piṭakas and Pāḷi Texts of the Buddha Era. It is undeniable that the face texts on Piṭakas in Pāḷi and those in Myanmar and skills and knowledge related texts such as classic text on prose and poetry, and medical fortune telling text, which were written by ancient poets and persons of letters belonging to periods from Bagan to late Konbaung, can still be studied until today, is due to the fact that palm leaf manuscripts have been cherished.

The palm leaf manuscript is valuable not only in terms of subject but also in terms of material. In former times, a palm leaf manuscript was made with difficulty on a step by step basis. A palm leaf manuscript indicates good characteristic of ancient Myanmar people such as their great diligence, their value on literature, their systematic behavior, their meticulous care, their patience, their wisdom and their devotion to religion.

Their religious literary works and the texts on poetry and prose by ancient poets, which can now be studied in today's printed words, were copied from palm leaf manuscripts.

Unless manuscripts had not remained, no text of ancient poets could have revived again. Therefore, palm leaf manuscripts and their background history will be presented to indicate how great the standard and value of palm leaves are.

1. The term of “Pe Sar”

The term “pesar” is a Myanmar expression which combines the two words “pe” and “sar”. “Pe” means leaves from the palm tree, and “sar” stands for words. Therefore, “pesar” is meant for palm leaves on which words are written. In this way, in Myanmar culture, “pe” and “sar” cannot be separated and “sarpe” (literature) come from “pesar”. In English, the expression “sarpe” is called literature, and “per sar” is palm leaf manuscript.

2. The distinction calls palm trees

Scholars accepted the fact that ancient Myanmar people used coryphe palm leaves and today palm leaves in writing. Myanmar people call toddy palm as “htan” and Mon people call it as “ta”. It is found that it is called “tā” or “tāla” in Pāḷi, Hindi and Sanskrit.

Ancient Myanmar people called coryphe palm as “pe” and Myanmar people of today call it as “pe”. Mon people call it “rai” or “rou”. The use of coryphe palm is not found in Pāḷi, Hindi and Sanskrit. The coryphe palm is a kind of palm and it is the same species with toddy palm, coconut, areca nut, nipa palm, date palm, saga palm and salō palm. It is referred to as a kind of grass (tiṇajāti) in the text of abhidhānappadīpikā.

Corypha palm and palmyra palm (toddy palm) grow in tropical regions and they are the same in shape. The former is bigger in trunk, its fruit is merely the size of an areca nut, and its leaf is broad and soft. The tiny fibers of the leaf of the latter are parallel and they easily tear, but those of the leaf of the former is like a network, and they do not easily tear. Therefore, the palm leaves seem to have been used in writing in former times.

The palmyra palm also grows as a staminate plant but the coryphe palm only grows as a pistillate palm. However, the former bears fruits every year whereas the latter bears fruits only once in its life. When the latter is eight or twelve years old, its leaves can be used. Its life span is approximately 60 years, and that of its leaves lasts up to a maximum of 1000 years.

The Piṭakas of Theravada Buddhism and ancient Myanmar literary works were recorded on palm leaves. Therefore, it is learnt that literature, fine arts, ways of living, customs, and religion which are the foundation of culture were not unrelated to palm leaves.

3. The history of Palm leaf Manuscripts

Scholars made assumptions in many ways as to the period in which palm leaf manuscripts were originally used. The periods that can be assumed as the origin of the use of palm leaf manuscripts in Myanmar and in foreign countries will be presented.

3.1 ŚriLañka

It is found as evidence that in ŚriLañka, palm leaf manuscripts were originally used in the year 450 B.E (BC 94). At that time, King Vattagāmaṇi contemporary to King Ngatapa ruling Śūkṣetrā reigned in Myanmar. The reason is that for the purpose of making the three Piṭakas, which are said to be the words of the Buddha, last long, they were put onto palm leaves. However, it should not be assumed that writing on palm leaves started from that time.

It is no little work to do to put the three Piṭakas onto palm leaves. It is obvious that one or two texts were written in ŚriLañka before. It is because the three Piṭakas had to be written in over 90 texts combining those in Pāli and commentaries on Buddhist Pāli texts. However, such over 90 texts are a set of the three Piṭakas, but numerous copies of the set had to be made for Buddhist monks residing all over ŚriLañka to study the texts.

A lot of tradition, methods and skill are needed to write so many texts. It can be assumed that even in times earlier than the year 450 B.E(BC 94), writings on palm leaves had been used. It was approximately the year 237 B.E (BC 307) when Shin Mahinda arrived in Sri Lanka to propagandize Buddhism. From that time, the people of Sri Lanka learnt the Piṭakas, and soon after the arrival of Shin Mahinda, the old commentaries on Buddhist Pāli texts are thought to have been translated into the language of Sri Lanka. Therefore, it is assumed that even before the year 236 B.E, the tradition of writing on palm leaves originated.

3.2 India

India should not be ignored as to literature. Although the evidence of literature about writings on palm leaves is not found, the use of literature can be assumed to have existed. It is a great nation in Asia in which cultures such as religion, philosophy, literary works, medicine and astrology flourished. If the tradition of writing on palm leaves flourished in Sri Lanka before the year 236 B.E, such a tradition must have existed in India even in the time of the Buddha earlier than that period.

The existence of writing on palm leaves in the time of the Buddha can be proved by the story of the rich man Ghosaka mentioned in commentaries on Dhammapada, who did not even read basic writings, the story of King Bimbisāra mentioned in Dhātuvibhaṅga Sutta, who presented King Pakkusāti from the kingdom of Thakatho a gold plate on which the three Gems were written, and the story of Vinaya MahāvaggaUpālidāraka in which the young man Upali's parents prepared to teach him the art of writing.

In addition, the subject mentioned in the text of Dhammaruddha Vinaya translated into Chinese was stated by Professor Jishilin as follows:

Sūra Bhikkhu, a kinsman of the tribe of Brahmaṇa, requested the Buddha to write the Buddhist texts in Sanskrit. However, the Buddha did not allow him to do so by saying that shoes texts in Sanskrit. However, the Buddha did not allow him to do so by saying that shoes texts would be spoil in the mixture of other languages. The language contemporarily dominant since the period of Buddhism flourishing was that of Brahmaṇa. Therefore, it can be assumed that the Buddha denied the writing of His sermons in Sanskrit, the language of Brahmaṇa.

It can be conjectured that writing mentioned above existed even during the lifetime of the Buddha in accordance with Chinese Buddhist literature, as referred by Professor Jishinlin. There is some more evidence of writing earlier than that. Approximately BC 1750 before the appearance of the Buddha, the people of Arayan entered India from the north-east region. Animist offerings which were their belief were included. The texts of Veda were written in order to have efficacy in making such offerings. Therefore, the tradition of writing is thought to have existed even before the appearance of the Buddha. However, there is no evidence found to prove on which objects such writing were used.

3.3 Myanmar

The fact as to how palm leaf writings were involed in the texts of Buddhism and in which ways they came to Myanmar people will be presented. The period in which the earliest writing in Myanmar was found was 101 B.E (BC 443) during the reign of King Duttabaung in the kingdom of Śrīkṣetrā. At that time, it is said in historical and religious texts that ArahatDeibathwe gave the king the text of the kingly code beginning with apāyagatimupayaṃ. Additionally, it is obvious that writing existed according to golden palm leaf manuscripts of Khinbakon excavated in the district of Śrīkṣetrā and the writings inscribed on Buddha images.

It is found that according to commentaries on VisuddhiMagga, Glass Palace Chronicles and writings of Piṭakas, in 956 B.E (AD 412), Shin Mahābuddhaghosa went to ŚrīLaṅka where he wrote commentaries. It said that after that time the texts by Shin Mahābuddhaghosa came to Thaton during the reign of King Dhammapāla. The fact about the arrival of Piṭakas in Thaton needs to be mentioned. At that time, the capital city of the people of Mon was Suvanṇabūmi (Thaton). It is said to have been a sea port and populous. The people of Mon traded with the peoples of Pallava, Indara, Celanga from India. From the latter, the former got the art of writing, architecture and fine arts, and cultures such as

Hinduism and Buddhism. The kings of Pallava lived in the city of Kiñcipura. It was a region where men of letters lived during the reign of such kings. Therefore, it should be noted that the people of Mon received the Piṭakas by trading with the king of Pallava rather than from Shin Mahābuddhaghosa.

It is accepted that according to the assumptions made by stone inscribers, Buddhism and Buddhist literature arrived in Myanmar from such cities as Madura, Tanzora and Kiñcipura even before its contact with Śrīlaṅka. It must be said that writing started depending on religion. The palm leaf writing was not found since the palm leaves were decayed. Shin Uttamasīri, writer of the text “Kappaliṅkāra” clearly stated that palm leaves were used in writing in Śrīkṣetrā in about the year 629. The monk said that at the end of the text, the stone cave of hermit collapsed and the writings from brass parabaik put in the stone box were copied onto wood parabaik. Then, the writings from wood parabaik were put to palm leaves, as he wrote.

Palm leaves coming across the sea arrived in Śrīkṣetrā, Myanmar. It should be noted that the palm leaves arriving in Śrīkṣetrā were earlier than the arrival of palm leaves of the three Piṭakas in Thaton from ŚrīLaṅka. Evidence about palm leaf manuscripts should be sought in Bagan in Myanmar, whose pagodas and stupas are still prominent and Buddhist culture flourishes. According to Glass Palace Chronicles, in the year 29, Śrīkṣetrā was ruined and divided into three groups: Pyu, Kanyan, and Myanmar. At that time, the people of Pyu lived together in 19 villages on the island of Bagan-yonhlut under the reign of King Samuddarit. The fact that the assumption is right is proved by the stone inscriptions in the language of Pyu found in Bagan. The golden palm leaves excavated from Kinbagone, the text of kindly code beginning with apāyagatimupāyaṃ written by Shin Deibahtwe to King Duttabaung, and the text of Kappāliṅkāra written by Ashin Uttamasīri, which indicate that the people of Pyu in the period of Śrīkṣetrā earlier than that of Bagan had writing. This fact has been mentioned before.

Therefore, it can be conjectured that in the Bagan period, the art of writing had developed since the reign of King Samuddarit. The writing of characters would have been received from the people of Pyu. When during the reign of King Anawrahta the Piṭakas arrived from Thaton, the people of Bagan became well-versed with writing, as it is concluded. However, Buddhism that came together with the people of Pyu from Śrīkṣetrā seemed to have changed in some way. Additionally, as regards arigyi, the writing in the Bagan period is also mentioned. These persons created a kind of writing they wanted in order to make people believe their beliefs put it onto a tree bearing trumpet flowers, covered it

with the tree's outer bark, and seduced people into finding it as if such finding were from a dream. Since the writing found was read, a misunderstanding occurred between the king and the people.

It is said by stone inscribers that in the year 420 (AD 1058), in the context of the stone inscription of Lettheshay Pagoda built by King Anawrahta, which was inscribed in the Myanmar language, the writing of the language started from that time. In particular, it is obvious that after the Piṭakas were received with the conquer of King Manūhā of Thaton, the tradition of writing on palm leaves flourished in Bagan. In other words, King Anawrahta himself spread the seeds of palm around the lake of Mya close to the foot of Taywin Hill, as said by historical records. Such writing developed more and more from the Bagan period through the periods such as Myinzin, Sagaing, Innwa, Taungngu, and Nyaungyan until the end the Kombaung period.

However, in the early colonial period, writing on palm leaves were no longer used since printing machines were in vogue, and the former only survived in rural areas. After the country gained independence, the tradition of writing on palm leaves vanished, and merely writing on buds of toddy-palm leaves by fortune tellers remained.

4. *Scrutinizing to be done "Pe"*

However, scrutinizing needs to be done as regards palm leaf manuscripts. In the celebration of the fourth Buddhist Council, Pāli was used in the texts of Sri Lanka such as Sāratthadīpanī and Mahāvamsa as in Potthakāroha, potthakāruḷhaetxc. In addition, Shin Uttamasīri of Śrīkṣetrā used Pāli expressions such as potthakamaṃaropeyyāmi in writing the text of Kappālankāra. Although Myanmar people wish to translate the expression pottaka as palm leaves, it is not found in Pāli with that sense. It seemed that writers on palm leaf manuscripts believe that even in the period of the appearance of writing, characters were written on palm leaves and nothing else could be used.

Nonetheless, to call "pesar" as "pe" is not acceptable. It is thought that wood, board, leather, cloth and paper on which writing is visible can be called "pe" because in Pāli, everything that can be written is called potthakā. When it was translated into Myanmar, ancient writers used it as "pe", "bud of toddy-palm leaf", "parabaik or writing table mad of paper, cloth or metal in the form of according folds", or "paper". Hluttaw Minister from Bagan U Tin stated in his paper on Myanmar King's Ruling System (5th volume, p.98) that "every cloth and object that can be written on is included in Potthakā".

In other words, a big piece of iron that can be struck by hammer is called “pe”. In this case, “pe” is something based. In brief, it is assumed that everything based for writing should be called “pe”.

Conclusion

Before the advent of printing in Myanmar, writing was used on flat stone, palm leaves, and parabaiks. In particular, palm leaves were mostly used. Palm leaves were easily available in large numbers and writing on palm leaves was easier than writing on flat stone.

In the stone inscriptions during the Bagan period, Piṭakas were written on palm leaves. It can be clearly seen as inscribed that palm leaves were bound and bundled with two pieces of wood and palm leaf bundles were in a wood container and donated. Ancient person of letters wrote palm leaves poems, verses, texts of prose like histories and stories. In the present day, however, palm leaf manuscripts are rarely seen since it is now the age of printing and computing. Only in ancient monasteries, large libraries and some departments can be seen palm leaf bundles. Although they are kept and seen there, they are so old. Some of them are so valuable that they are kept with care and system in order not to let them be broken and destroyed. Therefore, palm leaf manuscripts are in the hiding and new generations are not at all aware of their existence. However, palm leaf manuscripts contributed the interests of all the Myanmar people. Although such valuable and helpful palm leaf manuscripts were stopped, they are still honored under the name “pesar”.

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